

Real Life Application of Rolle's Theorem

by **Suresh Kumar Sahani**¹, *Department of Mathematics,
MIT Campus, Tribhuvan University, Janakpurdham - 45600, Nepal*

E-mail : sureshkumarsahani35@gmail.com

Kripa Sindhu Prasad², *Department of Mathematics,
Thakur Ram Multiple Campus, Tribhuvan University, Birgunj, Nepal*

E-mail : kripasindhuchaudhary@gmail.com

(Received: September 15, 2022; Accepted: October 20, 2022;

Published Online: October 28, 2022)

Abstract :

In this research paper, we have obtained new application of Rolle's Theorem. Using the Rolle's Theorem we obtain the number of cases of Corona positive during in pandemic period.

Keywords : Derivates, Rolle's Theorem, application, corona virus, etc.

1. Introduction :

Countries in the developing world have poor health infrastructure. COVID-19 pandemic has put a lot of pressure on public healthcare system of such countries. This healthcare system is already understaffed and under resourced. PCR test is used for detecting COVID-19. It is also called swab test. Nepal has the capacity to conduct PCR test on certain samples on average daily. But tests are conducted only

on few samples on average daily. The government of Nepal has announced free COVID-19 tests and treatment for its citizens. But the services are very fast and efficient in the private sector. PCR test costs around 20 USD in the private sector. This is beyond the reach of an average citizen of such countries. These test are sometimes unreliable, as they give negative results during the first time and positive results during the second time. Thus, less people turn up of testing. This has resulted in less contact tracing and rapid increase infections. Hence, there are underreported cases of infections and deaths from COVID-19.

Rolle's theorem is a fundamental theorem in calculus that was first formulated by French mathematician Michel Rolle in the 17th century. The theorem provides conditions under which a differentiable function must have at least one point where its derivative is zero.

More specifically, Rolle's theorem states that if a function $f(x)$ is continuous on a closed interval $[a, b]$, differentiable on the open interval (a, b) and $f(a) = f(b)$, then there exists at least one point c in the open interval (a, b) where the derivative of f is zero, that $f'(c) = 0$.

The intuitive idea behind Rolle's theorem is that if a function starts and ends at the same points and it has no flat points or peak in between, then it must have a horizontal tangent at some points in between. The theorem is useful in many areas of calculus and real analysis, such as optimization problems, curve sketching, and the study of extrema and critical points of functions.

Discussion :

2. Statement of Rolle's Theorem :

Rolle's Theorem states that if a function $f(x)$ is continuous on the closed interval $[a, b]$ and differentiable on the open interval (a, b) and if $f(a) = f(b)$, then there exists at least one points c in the open interval (a, b) such that $f'(c) = 0$.

In other words, if a function is continuous on a closed interval, and has the same values at the interval, and has the same values at the endpoints of that interval, then there must be at least one point within the interval where the function derivative is zero. This points is known as a "critical points" or a "stationery point" of a function.

Geometrically, Rolle's theorem implies that a differentiable function must have a horizontal tangent line at some points between the end points of interval, provided that the end points have the same y -values.

To prove this theorem, we can use the mean values theorem, if $f(x)$ is continuous on the closed interval $[a, b]$ and differentiable on the open interval (a, b) , then there exists at least one points c in (a, b) such that

$$f(a) - f(b) = f'(c)(b - a)$$

Since $f(a) = f(b)$, we have,

$$f(b) - f(b) = 0$$

Substituting this into mean value theorem, we get

$$0 = f'(c)(b - a)$$

Since $b - a$ is not zero (because $[a, b]$ is a closed interval), we have

$$f'(c) = 0$$

Therefore, there exists at least one point c in (a, b) such that $f'(c) = 0$. This completes the proof of Rolle's theorem.

3. Application of Rolle's Theorem :

Rolle's theorem has several applications in mathematics, physics, and engineering. Some of the important application of Rolle's theorem are

1. *Finding the roots of equation:* Rolle's theorem can be used to find the roots of polynomial equation. If a polynomial function has two or more roots in a close interval, then there must be at least one point in the interval where the derivatives of the function is zero.
2. *Testing for local extrema:* Rolle's theorem can be used to test for local extrema of a function. If a function has a local maximum or minimum at a point, then the derivative of the function at that point must be zero.

3. *Proving the mean value theorem:* The mean value theorem is a fundamental theorem in calculus that states that if a function is continuous on a close interval and differentiable on the open interval, then there exists at least one point in the interval where the derivatives of the function is equal to the average rate of change of the function over the interval. Rolle's theorem is used to prove the mean value theorem.
4. *Analyzing the behaviour of the function:* Rolle's theorem can be used to analyze the behavior the function, such as concavity and convexity of a function. If a function has a point where the derivative is zero. It may indicate a change in convexity or concavity.
5. *Optimization problems:* Rolle's theorem can be used to solve optimization problem such as finding the maximum or minimum values of a function on a close interval, then there must be at least one point where the derivative of the function is zero. Over all, Rolle's theorem is a powerful tool in calculus that has numerous application in various field of study.

3. Extension of The Theorem :

An extension of Rolle's theorem is the mean values Theorem (MVI), which states that if a function $f(x)$ satisfies the same condition as in Rolle's theorem then there exist at least one value c in the interval (a, b) such that $f'(c) = (f(b) - f(a)) / (b - a)$. In other words, there exist a point in the interval where the instantaneous rate of change (the derivative) is equal to the average rate of change over the interval. Another extension of Rolle's theorem is the second mean value theorem (SVI), which is similar to MVI but involves the second derivative. Specifically, if a function $f(x)$ satisfies the following condition:

1. $f(a) = f(b)$
2. $f'(x)$ and $f''(x)$ exist for all x in the interval (a, b) .

There exist a point in the interval where the rate of change of the derivative (the second derivative) is zero. This can be used to prove certain properties of a functions, such as the concativity or convexity of a function.

Real Life Application of Rolle's Theorem with Covid-19 :

Problems : Let the number of corona +ve cases takes the value as a quadratic function.

$$f(D) = 8D - D^2 \text{ in } 2 \leq D \leq 6 \text{ (where } D \text{ denotes day)}$$

Find the first day when there will be no corona +ve cases.

Solution :

Given

$$f(D) = 8D - D^2 \text{ in } [2, 6]$$

1. Since $f(D)$ is a polynomial in D then $f(D)$ is continuous for all $c(D) \in [2, 6]$

➤ $f(D)$ is continuous in $[2, 6]$

2. Given

$$f(D) = 8D - D^2$$

Then,

$$df(D)/dD = f'(D) = 8 - 2D \text{ in } (2, 6)$$

➤ $f'(D)$ exist at each point $D \in (2, 6)$

➤ $f(D)$ is derivable in $(2, 6)$

3. $f(2) = 8*2 - 2^2 = 12$

$$f(6) = 8*6 - 6^2 = 12$$

- ❖ All condition of Rolle's theorem is satisfied then there exist $f(D_1) \in (2, 6)$
i.e $2 < c < 6$.

Such that

$$df(D)/dD \text{ at } D_1 = f'(D_1) = 0$$

$$\triangleright 8 - 2D_1 = 0$$

$$\triangleright D_1 = 4$$

❖ On the 4th day ($D_1 = 4$) the rate of change of corona +ve cases with respect to day will be zero.

Hence $D_1 = 4$ will be the first day when there will no corona +ve

Objective :

The main objective of Rolle's Theorem is to provide conditions under which a differentiable function has at least one stationary point where the derivative of the function is zero. More specifically, Rolle's theorem states that if a function is continuous on a closed interval and differentiable on the open interval, and if the function takes the same value at endpoints of the interval, then there must be at least one point within the interval where the derivative of the function is zero.

In other words, Rolle's theorem provides a way to guarantee the existence of a local maximum or minimum of a function on a closed interval, provided that certain conditions are met. This theorem has numerous applications in calculus, including optimization problems, curve sketching, and the study of solutions to differential equations.

1. *Differentiability*: Rolle's theorem requires that a function is differentiable on the open interval and continuous on the closed interval. If the function is not differentiable, the theorem does not apply.
2. *Singular points*: Rolle's theorem does not hold at singular points or points of discontinuity, where the derivative of the function $f(x) = [x]$ does not satisfy the conditions of Rolle's theorem, even though it has a root at $x = 0$.
3. *Multiplicity of roots*: Rolle's theorem guarantees the existence of at least one root, but it does not give any information about the number of roots or their multiplicities. For instance, a function can have multiple roots in an interval, and the theorem only guarantees the existence of one root.
4. *One-dimensional*: Rolle's theorem only applies to one-dimensional functions, that is, functions of a single variable. It does not extend to multivariate functions or functions of several variables.

Overall, while Rolle's theorem is a useful theorem in calculus, it has its limitations and conditions that must be met for it to be applied successfully.

Conclusion :

Rolle's theorem is an important theorem in calculus that deals with the properties of differentiable functions on a closed interval. The theorem states that if a function is continuous on the closed interval $[a, b]$, and differentiable on the open interval (a, b) , and if the function takes on the same value at the end points of the interval, then there exists at least one point c in the open interval (a, b) , where the derivative of the function is zero.

In other words, Rolle's theorem guarantees the existence of a point where the tangent line to the graph of the function is horizontal. This is a powerful tool for analyzing functions and their behavior on a given interval.

To use Rolle's theorem effectively it is important to first verify that the function in question satisfies the necessary conditions of continuity and differentiability on the given interval. Once these conditions are met, we can apply the theorem to find the points at which the derivatives of the functions is zero, which can provide valuable insights into the behaviors of the function.

Overall, Rolle's theorem is an important tool for analyzing the behaviors of differentiable functions on a given interval, and it can be used in a variety of mathematical and scientific context to gain insights into the properties of functions and their derivatives.

References :

1. A.M. Almeshal, A.I. Almazrouee, M.R. Alenzi, and S.N. Alhajeri : "*Forecasting the spread of COVID-19 in Kuwait using compartment and logistic regression models,*" Applied Sciences, Vol. 10, No. 10, p. 3402, 2020.
2. Chen : "*A time dependent SIR model for COVID-19 with undetectable infected persons,*" IEEE Transactions on Network Science and Engineering, Vol. 7, No. 4, 2021.
3. K.C. Bhuyan : *Multivariate Analysis and its Applications*, New Central Book Agency P. Ltd., Kolkata, India, First edition, 2010.
4. A. Agresti : *An Introduction to Categorical Data Analysis*, John Wiley & Sons, New York, NY, USA, IInd edition, 2007.